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Evaluation of N management practices for irrigated transplanted rice in Pondicherry, India

R. Balasubramanian, S. Ramesh, D. Maniamran, S. Anbumani, B. Vijayalakshmi, D. Tiroutchelvame, and R.S.S. Hopper, M.S. Swaminathan Research Foundation, Pondicherry, India E-mail: rbala_india@yahoo.com

Insufficient and inappropriate fertilizer nitrogen (N) management may account for one-half to two-thirds of the gap between actual and potential yields. About two-thirds of India's rice soils are deficient in available N (Mahapatra et al 1985). Agronomic efficiency of applied N (AEN) in rice dropped from 16.8 in 1970-71 to 6.6 in 1989-90. Therefore, emphasis is placed on improving N use efficiency (NUE) in rice.

Optimal N management strategies aim to match fertilizer N supply with actual crop demand, thus reducing N losses and maximizing crop N uptake (Thiyagarajan 1997). The chlorophyll or SPAD meter can be used to monitor crop N status and to determine the right time for applying N on rice crops (Peng et al 1996, Balasubramanian et al 1999). The critical SPAD value below which N needs to be applied may vary with cultivar, season, planting density, and soil and plant nutrient status other than N (Balasubramanian et al 1999). Therefore, critical SPAD values have to be adjusted for specific crop-growing conditions.

Controlled-release fertilizers release nutrients at rates and concentrations that match the needs of plants at specific growth stages for maximum efficiency (Shoji and Gandeza 1992). To improve NUE, we evaluated the SPAD method and controlled-release urea (CRU) along with

local N management practices in on-farm trials in Pondicherry, India, in 1998.

Four field trials each were conducted in the 1998 dry season (DS, navarai: January to May) and wet season (WS, sornavari: June to September). Rice variety ADT37 (semidwarf) was used in the DS, and Chinna Ponni (improved local variety) in the WS. Treatments included a zero-N control, SPAD-guided N application, 20 kg N ha⁻¹ basal + SPAD-guided N application, a single basal application of 60 kg N ha⁻¹ as CRU (with 6% coating), and the farmers' practice of 150 kg N ha⁻¹ applied in three splits (50% basal, 25% at active tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation to flowering). The first four N treatment plots received irrigation water directly from the field irrigation channel. Each plot was surrounded by a good bund. The farmers' fertilizer plot was demarcated with four pegs adjacent to the other treatment plots. All plots received a basal application of 22 kg P and 42 kg K ha⁻¹.

In the SPAD-N treatments, leaf N status was monitored weekly starting from 14 d after transplanting (DAT) until first flowering. The youngest fully expanded leaf of 10 randomly selected plants from each plot was used for the measurement. Whenever the average SPAD reading fell below the set critical value of 35, N fertilizer was applied immediately. In the DS, the amount of N applied each time was 30 kg

N ha⁻¹ from the early to maximum tillering stage (14–28 DAT), 45 kg N ha⁻¹ from the maximum tillering to panicle initiation stage (29–48 DAT), and 30 kg N ha⁻¹ from the panicle initiation to flowering stage (49 DAT to flowering); it was reduced to 20–30 kg N ha⁻¹ for corresponding stages in the wet season.

Plant height recorded at physiological maturity varied with treatments (Table 1). Height ranged from 91.3 to 93.1 cm for CRU, followed by other treatments. The basal + SPAD-N treatment recorded the most panicles per unit area, closely followed by CRU. The lowest panicle number was recorded in the control.

Among the four N treatments, basal application of 20 kg N ha⁻¹ + SPAD-N produced the highest yield of 5.8 t ha⁻¹ in the DS and 6.3 t ha⁻¹ in the WS. Increased yields in the basal + SPAD-N treatment were mainly due to increased panicle number m⁻². These soils, with a control yield above 4 t ha⁻¹, require basal N application in addition to N topdressing based on observed SPAD values. This contrasts with observations at other sites in India. The CRU treatment recorded the highest straw yield, followed by basal application of 20 kg N ha⁻¹ + SPAD-N.

Gross return was computed based on the prevailing market value of inputs and produce, such as grain and straw. The

Table 1. Plant height, number of panicles m⁻², grain yield, and straw yield of transplanted rice, Pondicherry, India, 1998 dry and wet seasons.^a

Treatment	Plant height (cm)		Panicles m ⁻² (no.)		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
Control	76.9 c	75.1 d	376 c	392 d	4.1 d	4.2 d	5.6 c	5.9 c
SPAD-35 N	86.8 b	86.5 b	499 b	531 b	5.4 bc	6.0 b	7.1 b	7.4 b
Basal + SPAD-35 N	90.8 a	88.2 ab	537 a	568 a	5.8 a	6.3 a	7.6 a	7.7 b
CRU (6.0%)	93.1 a	91.3 a	523 a	542 b	5.6 b	5.7 c	7.8 a	8.1 a
Farmers' practice	84.9 b	83.1 c	488 b	507 c	5.2 c	5.6 c	7.3 b	7.5 b
SED	1.0	1.0	7	8	87	90	77	124
CD (5%)	3.0	2.8	19	23	253	261	223	362

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at CD 5% probability level. CRU = controlled-release urea, SED = standard error deviation, CD = critical difference.

highest gross revenues were recorded for the 20 kg N ha⁻¹ basal + SPAD-N (Table 2). This was followed by CRU. The net returns, computed by deducting the paid-out cost from gross return, followed the same trend as the gross return.

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Table 2. Gross and net returns (US\$ ha⁻¹) of transplanted rice under different N treatments in the 1998 dry and wet seasons.^a

Treatment	Cost of cultivation ^b		Gross returns		Net returns	
	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
Control	193 c	206 c	397 d	442 d	204 e	236 d
SPAD-35 N	209 b	219 b	527 c	573 c	318 d	354 c
Basal + SPAD-35 N	216 ab	226 ab	613 a	654 a	397 a	428 a
CRU (6.0%) ^c	221 a	231 a	584 b	615 b	363 b	384 b
Farmers' practice	218 a	228 a	566 b	607 b	348 c	379 b
SED	3.42	3.55	9.48	9.97	5.77	6.20
CD (5%)	7.46	7.74	20.66	21.74	12.59	13.51

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at CD 5% probability level. ^bCost of prilled urea = US\$4.77 50 kg⁻¹, assumed CRU price = US\$5.71 50 kg⁻¹ (20% more than PU), price of rice = US\$8.90-9.67 (mean = US\$9.28) 100 kg⁻¹ rough rice (selling price varies among farmers). CRU = controlled-release urea, SED = standard error deviation, CD = critical difference.

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Polymer-coated urea: an efficient controlled-release N source for irrigated transplanted rice

T.M. Thiyagarajan, S. Aruna Geetha, Mir Zamman Hussain, P. Saradha, and P. Janaki, DSSAC, TNAU, Coimbatore 641003, India; and V. Balasubramanian, IRRI

Fertilizer nitrogen (N) recovery in wetland rice is often low, ranging from 30% to 40% (De Datta and Buresh 1989), as N is lost through denitrification, ammonia volatilization, and/or leaching (Singh and Buresh 1994). Controlled-release fertilizers release nutrients at rates and concentrations that match the specific needs of plants at specific growth stages for maximum efficiency (Shoji and Gandeza 1992). To improve N use

efficiency (NUE), we evaluated polymer-coated controlled-release urea (CRU) in two field experiments conducted at the TNAU wetland farm in Coimbatore, India.

In experiment I, conducted in the 1997 and 1998 wet seasons (WS, samba: June to September/October), three irrigated transplanted genotypes were studied under five N regimes. Rice genotypes were selected to reflect contrasting grain types: ASD16 with short

bold grains, ADT36 with medium grains, and ASD20 with long slender grains. N treatments included a zero-N control, soil test and crop response-based N application (STCR-N) for a target yield of 8 t ha⁻¹, green manure (*Sesbania rostrata*) at 6.2 t fresh weight ha⁻¹ plus 150 kg N ha⁻¹ as urea (SGM + N), chlorophyll meter (SPAD)-based N application, and CRU with 4.5% polymer coating. N doses applied through CRU were 140 kg N ha⁻¹ (60% of STCR-N) in 1997